

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2021-22 academic year for BPT

HOSPITAL ADMINISTRATION

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

VALUE ADDED COURSE ON
HOSPITAL ADMINISTRATION
FOR BPT (2018 BATCH)
15 weeks (30 hours)

Course Objectives

1. To provide an understanding of the functions of management and administration of the healthcare.
2. To teach leadership and managerial skills that will positively affect performance as a healthcare manager.

CONTACT
0824-2429139

FOR MORE DETAILS :
deanphysiotherapy@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Course period	From June till September 2022, during 8 th semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 4 th year undergraduates (2018 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide an understanding of the functions of management and administration of the healthcare.
2. To teach leadership and managerial skills that will positively affect performance as a healthcare manager.

Module 1

Introduction: Branches of administration, Nature and scope of administration, How to be an effective administrator, Planning hospital administration as part of a balanced health care program, Principles of hospital administration and its applications to physiotherapy.

4 hours

Module 2

Planning and organization: Planning cycle, Principles of organizational charts, Resource and quality management, planning change –innovation; Financial issues including budget and income generation.

5 hours

Module 3

Hospital administration: Organization, Staffing, Information, Communication, Coordination, Cost of services, Monitoring and evaluation; National health policy and health care system in India.

5 Hours

Module 4

Organization of physiotherapy department: Planning, Space, Manpower, Other basic resources; organizing meetings, committees, and negotiations.

4 Hours

Module 5

Personnel management: Personnel performance appraisal system, Quality care delivery from the staff.

Material management: Pharmacy, Hospital waste disposal.

Quality assurance: Hospital acquired infection; Quality assurance through record review and medical audit; Public relations in hospital and human resource management.

12 Hours

Attendance Policy:

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

References:

1. Gupta J. D. Hospital Administration and Management- a comprehensive guide. 2nd ed. Jaypee Brothers, 2015.
2. Joshi D. C, Joshi M. Hospital Administration. Jaypee Brothers, 2017.
3. Francis C M. Hospital Administration. 3rd ed. Jaypee Brothers, 2004.
4. Davies, R and Macaulay. Hospital Planning and Administration, BMC.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

ADHARSH KS (5SU18PT002)

for completing the 15 week value added
course on "Hospital Administration" from
June till September 2022

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor
Course Instructor

Dr. Rajasekar S
Dean

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AISHWARYA N M (5SU18PT004)

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course on "Hospital Administration" from
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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

AMRITHA K (5SU18PT007)

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This Certificate is presented to

ANAGHA K (5SU18PT008)

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This Certificate is presented to

ANASWARA PURUSHOTHAMAN (5SU18PT009)

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This Certificate is presented to

ANJALI MURALEEDHARAN (5SU18PT010)

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ARCHANA A S (5SU18PT011)

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ASHIFA K A (5SU18PT012)

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ASHWAJAKSHI (5SU18PT013)

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This Certificate is presented to

AVINASH KUMAR (5SU18PT014)

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This Certificate is presented to

BLESSY MOL T T (5SU18PT015)

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This Certificate is presented to

BORKAR AMISHA VITTHAL (5SU18PT016)

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BRAHMECHA TANVI NARESH (5SU18PT017)

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BRUNDA N M (5SU18PT018)

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CHACKO PRITY PHILIP (5SU18PT019)

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This Certificate is presented to

CIRIL P BABY (5SU18PT020)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

FATHIMA THANWEENA (5SU18PT022)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

GOPIKA NANDAN N R (5SU18PT024)

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This Certificate is presented to

KADAM TRUPTI RAVINDRA (5SU18PT027)

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Certificate of Completion

This Certificate is presented to

MIDHUN YADUBALAN (5SU18PT030)

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This Certificate is presented to

MUHAMMED ASHRAF (5SU18PT032)

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MUSSAMMIL ABDULLA (5SU18PT033)

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This Certificate is presented to

NAJIL HASHAL A K (5SU18PT034)

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NEHA P K (5SU18PT036)

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PRATHEEKSHA (5SU18PT037)

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RAMYA (5SU18PT039)

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SALVI AASTHA TUSHAR (5SU18PT041)

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SHETTIGAR SUNIL VENKATESH (5SU18PT042)

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SHETTY SAKSHI SHEKHAR (5SU18PT043)

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SHREYA D S (5SU18PT046)

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STEEPHAN VARGHESE (5SU18PT047)

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SWATHIKA B R (5SU18PT049)

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TAMATTA SHANTI CHANDU (5SU18PT050)

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WAGHMODE RUCHITA SANJAY (5SU18PT051)

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